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Who is Koṇḍadeva?

An unknown author of an unknown text in Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā

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Key words: Koṇḍadeva, Bhāṭṭamatapradīpikā, Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā, dharmalakṣaṇa, vidhivāda ākhyātavāda

Introduction

The system of Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā (PM) is concerned with the interpretation of the Vedic sentences in order to arrive at the intended meaning of Veda which is decisively related to the correct performance of the rite. PM was first systemized by Jaimini who formulated the aphorism and divided it into twelve chapters, each having at least four sections. The aphorisms of Jaimini are explained along with suitable examples from the Veda by Śabara in his *bhāṣya* called *Śābarabhāṣya*. *Śābarabhāṣya* has been commented upon by Kumārila Bhāṭṭa in his magnum opus in three parts namely *Ślokavārttika*, *Tantravarttika* and *Ṭuṭīkā*. There is another commentary on the *bhāṣya* by Prabhākara Miśra who was a contemporary to Kumārila. These two are credited with pioneering of the two famous schools of PM namely the Bhāṭṭa school and the Prābhākara school. A third school was also initiated later by Murāri Miśra. Out of these the Bhāṭṭa school gained maximum popularity. This school has a great lineage of scholars and is largely studied and followed till date. Large number of works have been written by several authors belonging to this school. Out of these many works have remained unpublished lying in the form of manuscript. One such work is *Bhāṭṭamatapradīpikā*.

The name of the text is quite transparent. It is a text illuminating i.e. expounding (*prakāśikā*) the theories (*mata*) according to the Bhāṭṭa school of Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā. It has been written by Koṇḍadeva. This independent treatise mainly deals with exposition of topics such as the nature of injunction, prime-qualificandness etc., which are related to verbal-understanding (*śābdabodha*) according to the views of the Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā especially according to the Bhāṭṭa school.

1. Background

The first instance where the information about the present work and the author was first come across was in the Critical Bibliography of Mīmāṃsā named *Mīmāṃsāsakusumāñjali* written by Dr. Umesha Mishra. This is published as an appendix to the popular book *Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā* in its Sources by Ganganatha Jha¹. Dr. Mishra states that Koṇḍadeva was the pupil of Anantadeva II and identifies the author of the present text with the renowned author Koṇḍa (or Kauṇḍa) Bhāṭṭa of the celebrated work *Vaiyākaraṇabhūṣaṇa* and the sāra. Later we come across the information in the New Catalogus Catalogorum (NCC)². The work is also mentioned by Karl H. Potter in his *Encyclopaedia of Indian Philosophies*³.

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2. Apparatus

New Catalogus Catalogorum (NCC) identifies the present work as Bhāṭṭamatapradīpa (-pikā) and has placed it under the author Koṇḍubhaṭṭa(C. 1600 – 1660 A.D.)⁴ who is considered identical with Koṇḍadeva. NCC mentions the presence of the manuscripts of the said work at two places namely Government Sanskrit Library, Saraswati Bhavan, Benaras and Telugu Academy, Cocanada. There is no copy of the manuscript in Telugu Academy, Cocanada. However, one copy of this text is available in the Bhandarkar Oriental Research Institute (BORI), Pune. No other information could be found regarding any other copy of the present work in all the published catalogues and visits to manuscript libraries.

The first manuscript is from Bhandarkar Oriental Research Institute, Pune. The accession number of the manuscript is 624 of 1886-92. A detailed description of the manuscript is as follows:

Name	<u>Bhāṭṭamatapradīpikā</u>
Author	<u>Koṇḍadeva</u>
Folio	42
Lines per folio	10
Letters per line	42(approx.)
Size	10.3" X 4.7"
Starting from	Folio no. 1B
Ending at	Folio no. 42B
Beginning	श्रीगणेशाय नमः। गणेशकृष्णादिसुरान् प्रणम्य गुरुनपि श्रीमदनंतदेवान् ॥ श्रीकोण्डदेवः प्रकरोतिविद्वान्सातां मुदे भाट्टमतप्रदीपिकां ॥१॥
End	जुहोतीत्यादौ सप्तम्या प्रतीयमानगुणभावविरोधेन संनिपातित्वलाभाय पुरुषसंस्कारत्वमेव स्यादित्यूह्यं ॥
Colophon	इति श्रीपूर्वोत्तरमीमांसक श्रीकोण्डदेवकृतौ भाट्टमतप्रदीपिकायां आख्यातवादे वाक्यभेदापादानादिप्रश्नोत्तरापादानां-ताभिधानं समाप्तम् ॥
Material	Paper
Script	<u>Devanāgarī</u>
Remarks	<u>Clear handwriting</u> is <u>good margins</u> are given on both the sides.

The second manuscript is from Saraswati Bhavan library, Varanasi. The accession number is 29654⁵. A detailed description of the manuscript is as follows :

Name	<u>Bhāṭṭamatapradīpah</u>
Author	<u>Koṇḍadeva</u>
Folio	41
Lines per folio	9
Letters per line	48
Size	10" x 4.5"
Starting from	Folio 1B
Ending at	Folio 41A
Beginning	श्रीगणेशाय नमः। गणेशकृष्णादिसुरान् प्रणम्य गुरुनपि श्रीमदनंतदेवान् ॥ श्रीकोण्डदेवः प्रकरोतिविद्वान्सातां मुदे भाट्टमतप्रदीपिकां ॥१॥
End	जुहोतीत्यादौ सप्तम्याप्रतीयमानगुणभावविरोधेन संनिपातित्वलाभाय पुरुषसंस्कारत्वमेव स्यादित्यूह्यं । श्रीगोपीपतीरक्षत्वहर्निशं ।
Colophon	इति श्रीपूर्वोत्तरमीमांसकश्रीकोण्डदेवकृतौ भाट्टमतप्रदीपिकायामाख्यातवादारंभः समाप्तोयं ग्रंथः ॥
Material	Paper
Script	<u>Devanāgarī</u>
Remarks	Photocopy received is not very <u>clear handwriting</u> is <u>average margins</u> on both the sides.

3. Identity of the Author:

The benediction of the text mentions the name of the author as Koṇḍadeva⁶. And it mentions the name of his preceptor as Anantadeva.

3.1.View of Dr. Umesh Mishra

In this book Dr. Umesh Mishra states, “Koṇḍadeva was the pupil of Anantadeva II and the son of Rangoji Bhatta ... The only work of his on Mīmāṃsā known to us is the *Bhāṭṭamatapradīpikā*”⁷ Dr. Mishra identifies the author of the present text with the renowned author Koṇḍa (or Kauṇḍa) Bhaṭṭa of the celebrated work *Vaiyākaraṇa-bhūṣaṇa* and the *sāra*.

3.2.View in the New Catalogous Catalogorum(NCC)

The New Catalogous Catalogorum(NCC) cites the name of the author as Koṇḍadeva⁸ mentioning him as pupil of Anantadeva, and gives the reference of the entry Koṇḍu Bhaṭṭa. Thus, NCC also identifies the author of the text with the celebrated author Koṇḍu/Kauṇḍa Bhaṭṭa. Under the entry Koṇḍu Bhaṭṭa⁹, NCC mentions the present author as the son of Raṅgoji Bhaṭṭa who is brother of Bhaṭṭoji Dīkṣita, and also states that the author is the pupil of Anantadeva II which is based upon the information got

from the present work. NCC mentions eight works under his name namely *tarkaratna*, *padārthadīpikā*, *prauḍh-amanahpramodajanana*, *bhāṭṭamatapradīpa (-pikā)* (the present work on *mīmāṃsā*), *vaiyākaraṇa (siddhānta) bhūṣaṇa* and its commentary *sāra*, *vaiyākaraṇa-siddhāntadīpikā*, *tarkapradīpa* and *sphoṭavāda*.

3.3. View in Encyclopaedia of Indian Philosophies

The present text *Bhāṭṭamatapradīpikā*, is placed under the author Kauṇḍa Bhaṭṭa, even by Karl H. Potter in his *Encyclopaedia of Indian Philosophies*¹⁰. However, Potter has clearly mentioned the source of his information as the NCC. It can be seen that it is Dr. Mishra who first identifies the author of the present work with the celebrated author Koṇḍa Bhaṭṭa. However he does not mention the source of his information.

3.4. Other Evidences

Although Umesh Mishra and NCC identify Koṇḍadeva with Koṇḍa Bhaṭṭa, still some internal and also external evidences do not allow us to draw this conclusion.

Firstly, in the manuscript, both in the benedictory verse as well as in the three colophons, the name of the author has been mentioned as Koṇḍadeva and not as Koṇḍabhaṭṭa.

Secondly, At the end of the second section on *Vidhivāda*, the colophon in manuscript from BORI reads thus, इति श्रीपूर्वोत्तरमीमांसकश्रीमदनन्ददेवात्मजश्रीकोण्डदेवकृतौ भाट्टमतप्रदीपिकायां विधिवादः समाप्तः¹¹ This clearly states that Koṇḍadeva is the son of Anantadeva.

Thirdly, the manuscript from Benaras reads as अस्मत्तातचरणीय भाट्टालंकारीय¹² stating that the text *Bhāṭṭālaṅkāra* has been written by the father of the author of the present text. *Bhāṭṭālaṅkāra* is the famous commentary upon the text *Mīmāṃsānyāyaparakāśa* of Āpadeva, written by his son Anantadeva. Thus, here too Anantadeva and not Raṅgoji Bhaṭṭa, is known as the father of Koṇḍadeva. Moreover, in all the published works of Koṇḍa Bhaṭṭa we find the colophon running as रङ्गोजीभट्टपुत्रेण कोण्डभट्टेन (by Koṇḍa Bhaṭṭa who is the son of Raṅgoji Bhaṭṭa). The mention of his father as Raṅgoji Bhaṭṭa is missing in the present text. On the contrary Anantadeva is mentioned as the father of the author in one of the manuscripts as pointed out earlier. Further, Koṇḍabhaṭṭa has not mentioned Anantadeva as his teacher in any of his works. A careful analysis of these facts reveals that Koṇḍadeva is different from the celebrated author Koṇḍa Bhaṭṭa.

4. Genealogy of Koṇḍadeva

Koṇḍadeva the author of *bhāṭṭamatapradīpikā* is clearly the pupil of Anantadeva and is also his son. We do not have any other information about the author directly.

However, Anantadeva has mentioned his family lineage in his celebrated work *smṛtikaustubha*¹³. Based on these sources, the following family tree of the author can be drawn :

5. Date of Koṇḍadeva

Dr. P.V.Kane¹⁴ has determined the date of Anantadeva around the middle of the 17th century. Views of Anantadeva has been criticized by Khaṇḍadeva in his *bhāṭṭadīpikā*. The year of death of Khaṇḍadeva has been stated by his pupil Sambhubhaṭṭa as 1665 A.D. in Benaras. And Koṇḍadeva has refuted the criticism put forth by Khaṇḍadeva against his father. Thus taking into consideration the time of Anantadeva and Khaṇḍadeva, Koṇḍadeva can be comfortably said to exist in the period from the late seventeenth century to early eighteenth century, which may probably be stated as 1675-1725 A.D.

6. Works of Koṇḍadeva

Considering the above family lineage of Koṇḍadeva and the works authored by the members of his family, it is more likely that more works on Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā and especially *dharmasāstra* may have been penned by our author. However, presently only one work which is the present text *Bhāṭṭamatapradīpikā* is known as being composed by Koṇḍadeva.

Organization of the Text

The text is spread across forty two folios. There are three colophons in the BORI manuscripts mentioning the three sections in the text namely :

Section I : *dharmalakṣaṇa*¹⁵ (Definition of dharma)

This section mainly deals with the definition of *dharma* as well as *adharmā* clearly discussing the narrow application and over application of the same.

Section II : *vidhivāda*¹⁶ (Theory of Injunction)

This section discusses in detail the meaning of *vidhi* according to the views of the *Bhāṭṭas*. It also discusses the construction of *vidhi* along with the relation, bringing out clearly the verbal understanding generated by it. It also

states many objections raised by the opponents especially the logicians and refutes the same to establish the views of the *Bhāṭṭas*.

Section III : *ākhyātavāda*¹⁷ (Theory of Personal suffix)

The third section named *ākhyātavāda* discusses mainly the topic of prime-qualificandness of *bhāvanā* in verbal understanding (*śābdabodha*). As stated above, this section is just introduced in the manuscript. It is not complete.

An important discussion that would not be out of place here would be whether the said text is complete or incomplete. The present text bears a striking similarity in arrangement of topics as well as manner of dealing with the topics with *bhāṭṭatantrarahasya* of *Khaṇḍadeva*. If we compare the topics of both the texts it can be surely said that the original scheme of the author was bigger. However, irrespective of the original scheme of the author which might have been larger than the present text, there are no proofs to the fact that it was actually written by the author. Moreover, with respect to the topic that it deals with, namely the whole of *dharmalakṣaṇa*, *vidhivāda* and the discussion regarding the prime-qualificand in verbal understanding, the present text has completed the discussion. Hence it can definitely be said to be complete. Significance of the text

The text belongs to the neo-school of Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā. This is quite evident by the language and the *pariṣkāra-paddhati* adopted by the author. Koṇḍadeva himself claims the same in the text¹⁸ itself. The present text is one of the few texts of PM written in the neo style. As far as the topics are concerned, Koṇḍadeva has elaborated on many topics in great details such as the discussion on the smṛti from the Nirukta reading '*bhāvapradhānam ākhyātam*¹⁹'. This smṛti is very essential for PM to establish prime-qualificandness of *bhāvana*. In this text, Koṇḍadeva has also criticized at many places the views of *Khaṇḍadeva* who is the pioneer of the neo school of PM and whose views are widely accepted as authoritative. Koṇḍadeva has also initiated many original discussions in the present text. Some of the topics where there is significant contribution of the present text are a) Discussion on *dharmatva/adharmatva* of *śyena* b) Critical analysis in case of discussion on *ṣoḍaśigrahaṇa* c) Refutations of many views of not only the logicians but also the *mīmāṃsakas* such as *Khaṇḍadeva* at many places c) Providing new opinion on topics such as discussion on *pravṛtti/pravartanā* etc.

Conclusion

Koṇḍadeva the author of *Bhāṭṭamatapradīpikā* is different from the celebrated grammarian Koṇḍa Bhaṭṭa. Koṇḍadeva belongs to a family of authors who are an authority in Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā. Koṇḍadeva's only available

work *Bhāṭṭamatapradīpikā* adds to the knowledge base of the Sanskrit literature in general and to the system of Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā in particular. It unravels the technical aspects of the theories of neo-mīmāṃsakas. Koṇḍadeva's significance lies in adding new dimensions to the already established and mostly accepted views in Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā.

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- ¹ Benaras Hindu University, Varanasi, 1941.
- ² Vol. V, pg. 92.
- ³ Vol. XVI-*Philosophy of Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā*, pg. 505
- ⁴ Vol. V, pg. 92.
- ⁵ A Descriptive Catalogue of the Sanskrit manuscripts, Sanskrit University Library(Sarasvati Bhavan), Varanasi, Vol. VII pg. 274.
- ⁶ प्रणम्य गुरुनपि श्रीमदनन्तदेवान् । श्रीकोण्डदेवः प्रकरोति ... भाट्टमतप्रदीपिकाम् ॥
- ⁷ Pg. 58.
- ⁸ NCC vol.V,pg. 91.
- ⁹ ibid. pg. 92.
- ¹⁰ Vol. XVI- Philosophy of Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā, pg. 505.
- ¹¹ Folio no. 34B
- ¹² Folio no. 10B
- ¹³ *Smṛtikaustubha*, pp. 2-3
- ¹⁴ *History of Dharmasāstra*, vol.I part II, pg. 962.
- ¹⁵ इति श्री श्री कोण्डदेवकृतौ भाट्टमतप्रदीपिकायां धर्मलक्षणं समाप्तम् ।
- ¹⁶ इति श्रीपूर्वोत्तरमीमांसक... श्रीकोण्डदेवकृतौ भाट्टमतप्रदीपिकायां विधिवादः समाप्तः।
- ¹⁷ इति श्रीपूर्वोत्तरमीमांसकश्रीकोण्डदेवकृतौ भाट्टमतप्रदीपिकायां आख्यातवादे वाक्य-भेदापादनादि प्रश्नोत्तरापादनांताभिधानं समाप्तम् ।
- ¹⁸ नव्यमीमांसकस्य ममापि (Folio 10B from the text)
- ¹⁹ Nirukta 1.1.